

The \mathbb{C} Index Property.

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Abstract

This paper defines the property of \mathbb{C} Indices such that $n \in \mathbb{R}$ for all $\Omega_n \in \mathbb{C}$. Definitions and properties are stated in this paper.

1 Definitions of \mathbb{C} Indices

1.1 Definition of Ω

Let Ω_n be a set defined as $\Omega \in \mathbb{C}$ and the following indices $\beta \in \mathbb{C}$:

$$\Omega_n = (\beta_0 \times \beta_n) \tag{1}$$

1.2 Definition of α

Let α denote Ω_n with a remainder of \mathbb{X} defined as the result of β_n .

$$\alpha = \Omega_n \cup \mathbb{X} \tag{2}$$

2 Properties of \mathbb{C} Indices

2.1 Properties of Ω

1. $\Omega_n \cup \mathbb{X}$ such that $\mathbb{X} = \beta_n$.

2.2 Properties of α

1. $\mathbb{X} = \beta_n$ such that $\beta_n \in \mathbb{C}$